

IMPROVING THE TEACHING OF ORGANIC CHEMISTRY AT THE SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL LEVEL USING MULTIMODAL INSTRUCTIONS: A META-ANALYSIS

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Abstract

The students we teach learn differently and the way they learn is influenced by how teachers teach. West Africa Examination Council (WAEC) has documented that the performance of students in West Africa Examination keeps declining in chemistry paper, especially in the aspect of Organic Chemistry. There are severally studies that provide designs of intervention for curbing this problem. Again, in this digital environment, there are several ways of presenting information. This study sought to synthesis and analysis studies conducted on the impact of multimodal instructional approaches on senior high students' performance in Organic Chemistry. For this reason, a total of 15 studies were analysed including 5 theses and 10 published articles from 2009-2019. A purposive sampling method was used in the selection of theses and articles. This enabled the researcher to put in measures to include and exclude studies that do not meet the criteria. The criteria used for the review of studies were summed up to 10. They were key words, sample size, the year of publication, research scope, methodology, reliability and the validity of instrument, educational level and implications. Other criteria include method of data collection and data analysis techniques. Data was interpreted based on effect size. The results were presented using tables. The result indicated a moderate effectiveness of this multimodal instructional approach using Cohen's ranges. The moderators' analysis showed a statistically significant among the effect sizes of the studies ($d= 0.649$, $p=0.001$) on the impact of multimodal instructional on teaching Organic Chemistry.

Keywords: Multimodal Instruction, Effect Size, Meta-Analysis, Organic Chemistry
